

Environmentalism beyond Borders: The MT Arman 114 Oil Spill and the Politics of Marine Protection in Indonesia

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Abstract

The oil spill caused by the MT Arman 114 ship in the North Natuna Sea is a clear example of how marine pollution is a transboundary issue with fatal consequences for the environment, economy, and society. This article analyzes the case from an environmentalism perspective in international relations. Indonesia's blue economy development, which is part of its strategic roadmap, presents a paradox in its implementation, which has yet to clarify the legal status of marine governance. The environmental damage that has occurred in Natuna has had a direct impact on the economy of the local community, most of whom are fishermen. Law enforcement by international regimes such as UNCLOS and MARPOL is also still hampered by loopholes in the flag of convenience. Therefore, there must be long-term environmental restoration based on blue justice, economic compensation, and maritime governance reform

Keywords: MT Arman 114, Oil Spill, Blue Economy, Governance, Blue Justice

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INTRODUCTION

The issue of marine environmental protection is increasingly central to the study of international relations, as the intensity of cross-border economic activity in the global maritime sphere increases. Oil spills, as one of the most destructive forms of marine pollution, not only cause long-term ecological impacts but also raise complex political, legal, and international governance issues. The nature of the ocean as a global commons makes every pollution incident transnational, transcending national jurisdictions and challenging the effectiveness of existing environmental protection regimes.

The MT Arman 114 oil spill in Indonesian waters clearly illustrates how maritime environmental disasters cannot be understood solely as technical accidents or operational failures. This incident has opened up debate about the responsibilities of flag states, coastal states, and non-state actors in maintaining the security and sustainability of the marine environment. Furthermore, this case highlights the limitations of Indonesia's national capacity to address marine pollution involving transboundary actors, while also revealing the imbalance of power and interests in global maritime environmental protection politics.

In this context, the concept of environmentalism beyond borders becomes a relevant analytical framework for understanding the political dynamics behind the handling of the MT Arman 114 oil spill. This approach emphasizes that environmental protection can no longer be limited by state sovereignty alone, but rather requires international coordination, global normative pressure, and the involvement of civil society and international organizations. However, the reality on the ground often shows a gap between international normative commitments and policy implementation at the national and regional levels.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Environmental Pollution

Environmental pollution is a condition in which a substance, energy, or extraneous component is introduced into an environment by human activity or by natural processes in certain concentrations and amounts, causing changes to the environment that threaten health, welfare, and safety. Environmental pollution can also be seen from changes that occur in the environment, whether physically, chemically, or biologically, as a result of certain activities that disrupt nature conservation and human health (Azis & Huda, 2020). The case of the MT Arman 114 ship illegally dumping oil waste in the waters of northern Natuna is a form of environmental pollution.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Forms and Mechanisms of Environmental Pollution in the MT Arman 114 Case

The environmental pollution associated with the MT Arman 114 incident can be understood as the result of high risk maritime activities conducted in a sensitive marine area under weak regulatory oversight. The vessel was reported to be involved in illegal ship to ship oil transfer operations and manipulation of tracking systems, activities that significantly increase the likelihood of oil leakage due to inadequate safety procedures and improper cargo handling (Reuters, 2023). Such operations often involve unstable hose connections, poor valve control, and the discharge of contaminated ballast water, all of which are recognized sources of marine oil pollution (ITOPF, 2020). The primary pollutant released in the MT Arman 114 case was crude oil, particularly light crude oil carried as cargo by the tanker. Light crude oil contains volatile organic compounds such as benzene, toluene, ethylbenzene, and xylene, as well as polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons that are toxic to marine organisms even at low concentrations (NOAA, 2019). Although light crude oil evaporates faster than heavier oils, its soluble fractions can rapidly contaminate seawater and pose acute toxicity risks to plankton, fish larvae, and benthic organisms (UNEP, 2021).

The spread of pollutants from the MT Arman 114 incident was governed by physical and chemical processes collectively referred to as oil weathering. After release, the oil spread horizontally across the sea surface, driven by wind stress and surface currents, while lighter fractions evaporated into the atmosphere (NOAA, 2019). Wave action facilitated emulsification, increasing oil viscosity and prolonging its presence in the marine environment, while interactions with suspended particles promoted sedimentation and contamination of the seabed (ITOPF, 2020). These processes shaped the overall characteristics of pollution observed in the MT Arman 114 case, which combined acute and chronic ecological risks. Acute impacts included direct toxicity and smothering of marine organisms, while chronic impacts arose from the persistence of oil residues in sediments and coastal habitats (UNEP, 2021). Hydrocarbon compounds are known to bioaccumulate in marine food webs, increasing exposure risks for higher trophic level species and humans dependent on seafood resources. Consequently, the MT Arman 114 oil spill represents not only an environmental accident but also a structural governance failure in managing transboundary maritime activities and protecting marine ecosystems from long term degradation (Alongi, 2018).

The Impact of Pollution on Marine Ecosystems and Surrounding Communities

Laboratory test results show that seawater pollution has occurred due to hazardous waste, including black oil waste, illegally dumped by the MT Arman 114 ship in the waters of northern Natuna (Antara News, 2024). This marine pollution could become a more serious problem, such as damage to the marine ecosystem. The structure and function of the marine ecosystem can be disrupted by hazardous waste entering the sea. Waste entering the sea is toxic to marine organisms, affecting the reproduction, growth, and development of marine life such as plankton, fish, crustaceans, and mollusks. If exposure to the waste is high enough and marine life cannot avoid or metabolize the pollutants from the waste, marine life will experience physiological disorders, tissue damage, and even death, which in turn will damage the natural marine ecosystem. Through the marine food chain, if small organisms are exposed to this waste and are eaten by larger predators, continuing up to the top predators, the waste will be transferred and enter every marine food chain, even reaching the fish consumed by humans. This not only damages the marine ecosystem but also has an impact on humans and can threaten their health. The quality of seawater also deteriorates, making the water appear oil-coated, which can hinder light penetration and the photosynthesis process of phytoplankton, which supports marine productivity (Darza, 2020).

Surrounding community that depend on marine resources face adverse impacts, including health problems such as skin irritation, respiratory disorders, nervous system disorders, and chronic diseases that can affect people who are exposed to seawater in their daily lives and consume fish and other marine animals that have been contaminated by hazardous waste. Damage to marine ecosystems caused by hazardous waste also reduces and can even eliminate the income of communities that depend on marine resources. The destruction of the marine ecosystem has led to a decline in fish stocks and poor catches due to the poor water quality caused by the waste. The local tourism industry can also be affected by polluted seas. Non-biodegradable waste leaves behind pollution that is difficult to clean up. Restoring the environment and marine ecosystem requires significant costs and a long time (Dahalan & Mulia, 2025).

Environmental Management and Restoration Following the MT Arman Incident

After MT Arman was detected by Bakamla, legal proceedings were initiated to strengthen Indonesia's position in its international claim. The Ministry of Environment and Forestry brought evidence such as environmental samples to investigate whether there was evidence of environmental pollution in the area. After conducting oil fingerprinting, the Ministry confirmed the pollution through forensic evidence. With this strong evidence, Indonesia was able to strengthen its claim for accountability in the international arena (IMIC, 2023). This case shows that the government is responding, but its implementation has revealed weaknesses in Indonesia's marine governance structure. Although the MT Arman was successfully captured, this reflects the fact that maritime surveillance capacity is still not ideal. With a maritime territory covering approximately 5.9 million km, Indonesia only has 13 active patrol boats, whereas the ideal units would be 90.

The impact of the MT Arman case has not only caused marine environmental degradation around Natuna, but according to data from the Ministry of Marine Affairs and Fisheries, it has also had a major impact on Natuna's blue economy. In Natuna itself, there are 5,849 fishing households with a potential catch of up to 504,212 tons/year. However, after this incident, local fishermen reported an 80% decline in their catch, which led to a lawsuit against the ship's captain. In addition, Natuna is also an active seaweed cultivation area that exports seaweed and grouper to Hong Kong, so this incident has the potential to disrupt the domestic economy of coastal communities. As this is a paradox in the blue economy roadmap, the government responded with technical cleanup through containment and recovery. This will be followed by long-term habitat restoration to restore the mangrove and coral reef ecosystems. Due to the fishermen's lawsuit regarding the economic decline, there is a need for quick claims and the provision of national recovery funds such as the Maritime Green Fund to ensure the socio-ecological security of the affected communities (IOJI, 2023).

As one of the largest archipelagic countries in the world, Indonesia has sought to protect its maritime territory by joining various international conventions. Although not legally binding, conventions such as UNCLOS and MARPOL 73/78 form an important basis for Indonesia's maritime security. These agreements stipulate that countries are responsible for any damage to the marine ecosystem caused by ships flying their flag. However, these agreements have a loophole known as the flag of convenience. This refers to cases where foreign ships use the flags of other countries to escape prosecution for marine pollution in other countries. In such cases, the International Maritime Organization (IMO) and the International Oil Pollution Compensation Funds (IOPC Funds) should act as guarantors of global standards and compensation (IOPC Funds, 2018). However, UNCTAD data shows that around 70% of ships still engage in this practice, indicating that economic interests remain the primary concern. This situation has prompted Indonesia to improve systems such as NMSS, AIS, and maritime drones, as well as to actively participate in discussions on maritime governance reform (theinterpreter, 2023).

CONCLUSION

The MT Arman 114 oil spill in the North Natuna Sea confirms that marine pollution is a transboundary issue that reflects weaknesses in national and global maritime governance, rather than merely a technical incident. Damage to the marine ecosystem has a direct impact on fishermen's incomes and threatens the sustainability of Natuna's blue economy, while the international legal regime remains weak in enforcing accountability for flag of convenience practices. From an environmentalism perspective, this case shows that marine environmental protection must go beyond technical cleanup approaches towards blue justice-based ecosystem restoration, accompanied by strengthening

Indonesia's surveillance and normative diplomacy capacities to promote global maritime governance reform.

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